

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

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RECYCLING TIRES OF USED VEHICLES AND MANUFACTURING ROADS ON THEM

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Abstract

This scientific article examines the technology of processing used vehicle tires and the development of road surfaces based on them. In addition, the normative requirements of the technology for the processing of car tires are expressed. The physical and chemical properties of local raw materials and industrial products for the processing of used vehicle tires and the production of road surfaces based on them were determined.

Keywords: worn tires, secondary tire interpretation, environmentally safe recycling technology, road mats, synthetic rubber, rubber waste.

Urgent tasks is the complexity and sharp increase in the process of operation of vehicles and the use of environmentally friendly, inexpensive materials. The number of cars in the world is growing steadily and the destruction and recycling of tires is becoming of great environmental and economic importance for all developed countries in the world.

This is primarily due to the fact that worn tires are a source of environmental pollution for a long time. In addition, rubber is flammable and biodegradable, and a stack of rubber tires is a great place for rodents and insects to congregate, a source of many infectious diseases.

The advantage of tire processing is that 80% of the world's tire reserves are made from synthetic rubber, which is a non-renewable natural resource derived from oil. Here, instead of storing, burying and burning, the technology of recycling them is of great economic importance, because in this case valuable raw material reserves are preserved, resources are saved, cheap technologies are developed and environmental conditions are improved, large areas for rubber waste disposal are not needed.

It should be noted that rubber tires and coatings made from natural resources will already be composed of self-supporting materials: metal, textile, regenerate and others. Therefore, there is a widespread area of use of these tire components.

Determination of physical and chemical properties of local raw materials and industrial products for the processing of used vehicle tires and the production of road surfaces on their basis;

Processing of used vehicle tires and based on them to prove the effect and physicochemical properties of the components in the composition of road surfaces;

Processing of used vehicle tires and determination of cold and heat resistance and operational properties of road surfaces on their basis;

Development of the procedure and technology for processing used vehicle tires and obtaining pavements based on them .

The first stage, international and local scientific research and experiments in this field will be analyzed . The physical and chemical properties of industrial products for the production of pavements using components of the liquid composition will be determined using secondary tire grinded.

The second stage, using the secondary tire interpretation, the new road surfaces of the components of the liquid composition are determined by cold and heat resistance and operational properties, and the State Standard is developed.

The third stage is the creation of the composition and technology of obtaining the components of the liquid composition using a secondary tire interpretation. Laboratory research, experimental results and Standards will be developed at the Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute and Jizzakh Free Economic Zone. As a result of scientific research, technical conditions and technical regulations will be developed.

Normative requirements of technologies for processing of car tires The materials used for laying the base and pavement layers of the road surface are selected in accordance with the requirements of the relevant normative documents for each of them.

It is necessary to ensure that the rollers used for compaction of the pavement, pavement and base layers move from the edge of the road to the middle, and during this movement the trail of the roller passes at least 1/3 of the previous walking trail. The speed of the roller in the first 2-3 passes should be 1.5-2 km per hour, unless otherwise specified in these rules, and then at the end of the slow acceleration compaction should be equal to the working speed of the roller specified in the passport. The number of passes of the cathode and the thickness of the compacted layer, the reserve coefficients in the compaction are determined by additional test transitions, the results of which are recorded in the work logs.

Quality control during the construction of the road surface is carried out by inspecting each layer in turn and taking the following measurements at a distance of at least every 100 m:

- height measurement along the road axis;
- width;
- the thickness of the uncompressed layer of material along the axis;
- smoothness (3-meter road under the rail, 5 points at a distance of 0.75-1.0 m from the edge of the base, cracks under the rail at the ends of the rail and at a distance of 0.5 from each other).

A list of other inspected measurements and their controls are provided in the relevant sections of these regulations. During inspection, new, fast measuring instruments can be used, the readings of which correspond to the measurements of the instruments used continuously.

When widening a paved road under repair, it is necessary to ensure that the newly laid pavement is tightly and evenly bonded with the old pavement.

When working in roadside quarries, it is necessary to consider the collection of rocks and, if necessary, the enrichment of crushed rocks of different strengths with rock materials in terms of strength, size and purity. Measures should be taken to prevent the rocks from freezing and hardening with each other in year-round quarries.

Usually in the reconstruction of bridges joints imported materials with closes. Rubber interpretations apply through material costs noticeable degree save because it is possible processed from the tires is obtained.

Rubber grinded, rubber products functional extractor enterprises, rubber mills, roads repair companies replace cheap rubber pressing rubber grinded needy which was oil again performance factories by demand is done.

Tires again performance process a how many very much heavy from work consists of.

This step all tires smaller segments split includes. That's it for usually following tools use:

- press guillotines;
- hydraulic shears;
- mechanical / disc shears;
- mechanical cutters.

In the world today, many high-strength high-molecular-weight compounds and products are obtained from powdered carbon materials and used in chemistry, food, machinery, aerospace, electrical equipment, and military equipment. It is important to create powdered carbon materials that form the structure of products obtained on the basis of high-molecular compounds on the basis of pre-specified technological, physical-mechanical and dynamic properties. Creation of carbonaceous substances to improve the technological, technical and specific properties of high-molecular-compound products in the world, modification of ingredients in high-molecular-composite compositions based on them and high-strength organic acids and solvents, radiation, heat, cold, used in various conditions and research into the production of friction-resistant technical products, the composition of the composition and the creation of

a scientific basis for production technologies. The powder from recycled tires is widely used. We will consider the following main areas of use of this material:

The number of cars on the roads of our country is growing day by day, as a result of which the amount of used tires is also increasing. At this point this tires what to do need he said of course question appear will be Well, the tires how so again performance is it possible Most people tires simply waste leave they send. With the help of a mobile plant for the processing of car tires, it is possible not only to free large areas of tires, but also to obtain from them the necessary raw materials (rubber, metal). The recycling of tires is also important because even a much older tire can be used as a good polymer raw material.

Environmental protection measures should be taken during the construction and reconstruction of roads. When making technological solutions in production, it is necessary to take into account that they do not harm the environment, do not disturb the balance of nature, do not pose a risk of changes in environmental, geological, hydrological and other natural conditions. Drainage drying and leveling works that damage the grass growth layer outside the area allocated for road construction are prohibited.

Conclusion: Temporary structures in the area allocated for road construction should be remedied from the construction, construction of roads, as well as in areas where parking, storage of materials and other similar lands are damaged until the road is put into operation. In the selection of production methods and mechanisms, it is necessary to consider the relevant sanitary norms, permissible standards of pollution of the environment and water basins, to completely eliminate or minimize other damage to the environment and lands, causing pollution. Warehouses where organic binders are stored must be equipped with heating devices to heat the binders, oils, and to maintain the same temperature in the bitumen pumps and bitumen boilers in bitumen pipes and cranes. Stone materials (gravel, gravel) should be unloaded as much as possible on bunker (semi-bunker) devices or closed warehouses around the rails.

In the yard of asphalt concrete, cement concrete plants, mixing equipment, rails and coastal warehouses, the surface of mineral storage areas should be covered with a hard coating to ensure drainage. Road pavement construction should only be carried out on a properly paved, ready-made, moisture-proof and durable pavement layer. When the base and pavement of the road surface is treated with binders, it is laid on the surface of a dry and clean layer, when treated with organic binders, the substrate must not be frozen. Before laying each layer of road pavement, it is necessary to measure their boundary section and height mark and fasten them in place with pegs. When machines equipped with automated tracking parts are used, the height and boundary markings are determined by means of tensioned wires on two or one side of the layer being laid. Linking the signs in place and checking that they are done correctly is done with geodetic instruments. During the winter, road construction layers are allowed to be carried out only at the foot of the road, which has been

fully completed and accepted until the onset of cold weather.

Before laying the road surface in winter conditions, it is necessary to clean the surface of the area of the sidewalk or the lower layer of the pavement from the snow and ice. It is forbidden to carry out the specified work when it is snowing and blizzard, as well as when the ice begins to melt.

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DEVICE FOR POSTING THE SENSITIVITY GRAVIMETER AXIS

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Abstract

Angle measurement means are one of the advanced directions for the application of gas ring lasers. The requirements of ring lasers used in angle measurement devices are different, in many respects, from those used in navigation. A simple ring laser developed for implementation in high-precision angle measurement instruments is described. The main specifications are presented. Methods of the accelerated tests are imperfect for determining a term of storage; therefore, tests during a real storage term remain the most reliable. Operation of the ring lasers in angle measuring instruments during 20 years has demonstrated their high stability. Using the described ring laser the angle measurement means of accuracy that exceeds an accuracy of the existing National Standards for a plane angle can be developed.

Keywords: aviation gravimetric system, ring laser, gravimeter, angle measurement systems.

Stating of the problem. The basic components of aviation gravimetric system (AGS) for measuring gravity anomalies are proposed in [1]. Those are devices for measuring speed and location coordinates of the aircraft, devices for measuring the height and gravity and airborne digital computer. Gravimeter is a sensitive element of AGS that measures the gravity and the accuracy of which, basically, determines the accuracy of all AGS.

A new piezoelectric gravimeter that has greater accuracy from known aircraft gravimeters is proposed in [1, 2, 3].

The accuracy of the previous posting gravimeter sensitivity axis significantly influences on the accuracy of AGS gravimeter. Therefore for precision posting gravimeters axis proposed use laser angle measurement device [3].

Ring lasers can be used in angle measurement devices of different purposes.

A significant attention is paid to the development of goniometers. For example, in [4, 5] the designs of goniometers as well as test results are described. In [6]

a specialized goniometer used in workshop conditions for the measurement of polygons angles is described. In [5] the first commercial automatic angle measurement system (goniometer-spectrometer) GS1L is described. The system is designed for the measurement of plane angles and pyramidity of the prism faces as well as refractive index of optical media. This system is produced in lots and widely used at many plants and metrological centers. With using a ring laser for such instruments as devices for the measurement of involutes profiles of tooth spiral of gear wheels [6] and a device for reproducing of linear accelerations are developed.

On the basis of ring lasers it is also possible to develop automatic devices for the measurement of shaft rotation angles, devices for checking the angle parameters of limbs, modulators, circular optical encoders and other angle structures, as well as devices for determining the angles between marks, stars, geodesic and astronomical devices, laser location devices and others. The advantages of ring laser